

**SELECT THE OPTIMAL PRODUCTION WASTE OF MALT ROOTS FOR
OBTAINING GLABRIDIN**¹A.I. Sanoev, ²O.T. Juraev, ³R.M. Khalilov, ⁴Sh.Sh. Sagdullaev^{1,2,3,4}Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances named after. acad. S.Yu. Yunusova Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, st. Mirzo Ulugbek, 77, Tashkent, 100170 (Uzbekistan),
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Abstract. *Glabridin is the main biologically active phytocomponent of Glycyrrhiza glabra L. Although glabridin is one of the most studied flavonoids in licorice, the main literature is devoted to its biological activity, but there is a lack of data on its isolation methods, technology and standardization. In this work, the effect of estrogens on the yield of glycyrrhizic acid and glabridin contained in raw materials was studied and analyzed, when processing licorice root in various ways, and also find the optimal waste from this production for the production of glabridin. As a result of the research, it was found advisable to use production waste (meal) from enterprises using water or 10% ethyl alcohol as a solvent to obtain glycyrrhizic acid and its salts from licorice root when producing glabridin. It has been established that the content of glabridin does not change during drying using methods at 60°C of non-vacuum drying (30 hours), vacuum drying (24 hours) and natural drying (72 hours) as optimal drying conditions for using this production waste (meal) as raw materials. It has been proven in the process of obtaining glabridin from raw materials that ethyl acetate and 96% ethyl alcohol can be used as an estrogen.*

Keywords: *Glabridin, glycyrrhizic acid, isoflavan, Glycyrrhiza glabra L, production waste, drying, vacuum.*

Introduction

In modern conditions of a market economy, the priority problem is the full use of raw materials. An important role in solving this problem should be played by the organization of rational processing of plant raw materials for use in the production of pharmaceutical and food industries. Nature has always been a great source of medicinal substances, providing us with various medicinal plants that produce valuable phytochemicals. Licorice is scientifically known as *Glycyrrhiza glabra* and belongs to the legume family. This medicinal plant is found throughout Asia as well as in areas of Europe [1].

In Uzbekistan, this plant grows in the floodplains of the Amudarya, Syrdarya and Zarafshan rivers and on the banks of their tributaries (in Tashkent, Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Bukhara and Surkhandarya regions). Rising to the middle mountain belt to an altitude of 2000 m above sea level, licorice in some places forms almost pure licorice thickets [2].

Based on the results of the expedition carried out by the IHRV of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tracts of licorice thickets were identified on the territory of Uzbekistan. It has been established that the largest commercial area of licorice thickets is located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and amounts to more than 15,000 hectares [3].

The main biologically active substances of licorice root are triterpenoid compounds, mainly glycyrrhizic acid and flavonoids, the content of which is up to 25% and 5% of the raw material, respectively [4-7]. In total, about 400 compounds have been isolated from licorice,

including about 300 flavonoid compounds [8]. This shows that the roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* can serve as a source for obtaining biologically active substances based on flavonoids, including glabridin, glabranol, liquiritin, isoliquiritin, liquiritoside, etc. [9, 10].

In recent years, there has been great interest in the world phytochemistry to the flavonoid glabridin. This substance inhibits the activity of the enzymes tyrosinase, DOPA-chromium tautomerase and spontaneous transformations, and also prevents the formation of melanin [11,12,13]. Therefore, various products from the roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* containing glabridin are widely used in the pharmaceutical, cosmetic and food industries [14, 15].

Considering that the roots of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* are mainly used on a large scale in the production of glycyrrhizic acid or its salts, the meal from these industries is a promising raw material for the production of dry extracts containing glabridin. In the future, it is necessary to standardize the raw materials for obtaining the glabridin substance from the waste of this production. To do this, it is necessary to analyze the effect of solvents on the production of salts of glycyrrhizic acid and glabridin from licorice root in different ways, and then select raw materials from these production wastes, study the methods of drying the selected raw materials and the factors influencing this process.

Our goal is to study and analyze the effect of estrogens on the yield of glycyrrhizic acid and glabridin contained in the raw materials; when processing licorice root in various ways, we also find the optimal waste from this production to obtain glabridin.

Materials and methods

The object chosen was licorice root, collected in November 2022 from the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the production of glycyrrhizic acid and its salts.

Currently, the isolation of glycyrrhizic acid from licorice root is mainly used as an extractant in water, ethyl alcohol solutions and other solvents. We studied and analyzed the effect of estrogens on the yield of glycyrrhizic acid and glabridin contained in raw materials when processing licorice root in various ways. The content of extractive substances was determined by the gravimetric method [16].

To do this, 1.0 kg of licorice roots with a particle size of 4-6 mm were placed in extractors and extracted five times under the same conditions with different estrogens. After this, the resulting extracts were filtered, dried, and residual - secondary products (meal) were analyzed. (Table -1).

The data presented in Table -1 show that when extracting glycyrrhizic acid and its salts with a 0.5% ammonia solution and 20-30% ethyl alcohol, the glabridin flavonoid is combined with glycyrrhizic acid as an extractive substance. Although the loss of glabridin during extraction in 10% ethyl alcohol was low, the yield of glycyrrhizic acid was also low. The lowest loss of glabridin and the highest yield of glycyrrhizin were observed during extraction with water at a temperature of 60°C. The highest yields of glabridin were observed in studies with 96% ethyl alcohol, n-butanol and ethyl acetate.

Table 1

Effect of solvent on the yield of glycyrrhizic acid and flavonoid glabridin

Extrogents	Yield of dry matter, % by weight of raw materials	Yield of glabridin, % by weight of raw materials	Yield of glycyrrhizic acid, % by weight of raw materials
Purified water, at a	20,4	4,4	94,2

temperature of 60°C			
0.5% ammonia solution in water at room temperature	30,0	25,5	94,3
10% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	22,6	8,8	78,8
20% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	26,8	18,8	87,6
30% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	32,5	26,7	95,2
80% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	18,8	82,7	25,5
96% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	14,6	96,6	5,6
Ethyl acetate at room temperature	6,2	95,4	0,9
Butyl alcohol at room temperature	10,4	95,6	1,6

Further, to select the optimal extractant from industrial waste for the production of glabridine, 96% ethyl alcohol, n-butanol and ethyl acetate were extracted. The results are shown on Table-2

Table 2

Effect of solvent on the production of flavonoid glabridin from industrial waste of licorice roots

Extrogents	Dry matter yield, % by weight of raw material	Glabridin yield, % by weight of raw materials
96% ethyl alcohol at room temperature	5,2	96,05
Ethyl acetate at room temperature	4,7	94,2
Butyl alcohol at room temperature	6,4	95,6

However, high extractives were observed in n-butanol extracts. This indicates that the extract contains a large amount of foreign substances other than glabridin and the purification of such extracts at subsequent stages becomes difficult. Since the results of ethyl acetate and 96% ethyl alcohol were close to each other, we decided to select these solvents as estrogens for further work.

Based on the experimental results, it was concluded that it is advisable to extract glycyrrhizic acid with purified water at a temperature of 60°C and subsequently extract glabridin from the waste of this production; ethyl acetate and 96% ethyl alcohol were chosen as estrogens. [17].

In order to standardize production waste, we conducted research on drying methods and factors affecting drying.

Waste from the production of licorice roots was dried under natural conditions for the first time.

- in a drying unit operating without vacuum, in a stream of hot air with a temperature of 60±5°C;

- in a drying apparatus under vacuum 0.6-0.8 kgs/cm², at a temperature of 60±5°C;

- using an infrared drying device;

The results obtained are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Changes in glabridin content and time in licorice root production wastes with drying methods

Drying methods	Amount of glabridin in licorice root production waste, %	Drying time, hour.
Non-vacuum drying, 60±5°C	0,31	30,0
Vacuum drying 0.6-0.8 kgs/cm ² , 60±5°C	0,32	24,0
Drying using infrared light	0,26	18,0
Natural drying	0,31	72,0

Table 3 shows that infrared radiation negatively affects the yield of the flavonoid glabridin in raw materials. Drying under non-vacuum conditions, vacuum conditions and under natural conditions, the content of glabridin does not change, only the drying time of the raw material is different. Subsequent drying of raw materials by these methods does not affect the glabridin content.

Conclusions

As a result of the research, it was found advisable to use production waste (meal) from enterprises using water or 10% ethyl alcohol as a solvent to obtain glycyrrhizic acid and its salts from licorice root when producing glabridin. It has been established that the content of glabridin does not change during drying using methods at 60°C of non-vacuum drying (30 hours), vacuum drying (24 hours) and natural drying (72 hours) as optimal drying conditions for using this production waste (meal) as raw materials. It has been proven in the process of obtaining glabridin from raw materials that ethyl acetate and 96% ethyl alcohol can be used as an estrogen.

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